

Macroscopic Insights of IoT Botnet Dynamics via AS-level Tolerance Assessment

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Abstract—The ubiquitous integration of the IoT in current sociotechnical systems alongside the manufacturing of IoT devices and IoT-enabled services equipped with minimal security, has profoundly altered the cyber-threat landscape. Consequently, the overwhelming majority of cyberattacks utilise compromised IoT devices as a vessel for initiating large scale volumetric (e.g., DDoS) or stealthy Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) such as ransomware through well orchestrated IoT botnets. Due to the constantly evolving nature of these botnets and their diverse structural characteristics, tracking their activities poses considerable challenges since malicious actors and botnet owners often adopt new strategies to evade detection and expand their botnet network. Evidently, Autonomous Systems (ASes) and their implied organisational and regulatory properties play a crucial role in botnet propagation. In this paper, we present a novel and extensive macroscopic measurement study quantifying AS-level tolerance in the context of IoT botnet behavioral dynamics across the global IPv4 address space. In order to verify and justify our hypotheses in terms of AS-level tolerance we conduct a longitudinal analysis over 3.8M malicious events triggered by IoT botnets across over 8K ASes using measurements gathered through globally distributed honeypots, IP blacklists and Internet regional registries for a three year period. We argue that the findings in the herein work can greatly benefit a range of stakeholders designing, operating, and managing current defense mechanisms as well as contributing significantly towards the evolution of next generation cyber defense mechanisms.

Index Terms—IoT botnets, Internet measurements, Autonomous Systems, Cyber security, Cyber Threat Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of malware specifically designed for IoT devices is a major concern for the overall Internet ecosystem. IoT devices, such as smart home appliances, wearable technology, and other Internet-connected devices, are increasingly becoming targets for malicious actors. The emergence of IoT botnets has raised concerns about the potential for widespread disruption and damage to critical infrastructure, as well as to the privacy and security of individuals and organizations. Hence, the proliferation of these types of attacks highlights the urgent need for improved security measures and

greater awareness among network operators about the risks posed by IoT-based threats. The highly heterogeneous nature of IoT devices and their broad deployments have resulted in the emergence of numerous security issues and measurement-based difficulties which strongly impede the collection, analysis and correlation of large-scale IoT-oriented data. Therefore, it is significantly important to build ground truth data empirically and further conduct macroscopic measurement-based analyses such as to adequately attribute Internet infrastructure fundamental routing and traffic dynamic properties [1].

IoT botnets are networks of compromised IoT devices ('bots') that have been infected with malware and are under the control of either an individual malicious entity or coordinated groups of 'hacktivists' [2]. These interconnected devices, also known as "bots," can be leveraged to conduct large-scale cyberattacks, including distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, spam campaigns, or cryptocurrency mining. Evidently, such botnets span across the Internet and they are present across a range of Autonomous Systems (AS) promoting distinct policies [3]. To this end, our work aims to underscore the properties of AS inter-domain routing policies on malicious activity originating from IoT botnets.

Analyzing the dynamic characteristics of IoT-based botnet is a challenging aspect demanding a comprehensive and broad view of the Internet [2], [4], [5]. In parallel, it is of crucial importance to consider vital functionalities of the global Internet such as AS-level routing to relate modern attack vectors and attribute them to recent trends that are aligned with the geolocation of attack vectors on the global Internet such as cyberwarfare. AS-level properties are crucial for the overarching functionality of the Internet and their exploitation by attackers has proven to be an effective means for botnet propagation. Through the distinct analysis and attribution of AS-level properties in regards to IoT botnet propagation and evolution it will be feasible to: (i) properly inform governmental and industrial bodies responsible for infrastructure defense and (ii) provide advanced information to automated Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) systems, intrusion detection and

prevention systems for adapting in new and evolving large-scale threat vectors. Consequently, enable enhanced attack attribution in terms of botnet scanning, establishment, and propagation techniques of new botnet variants.

In this paper, we provide a novel macroscopic analysis and provide unique insights in regard to the tolerance level some ASes could promote in the context of IoT botnet establishment and propagation. Our analysis is conducted over a comprehensive and real dataset gathered by globally distributed honeypots, IP blacklists and Internet RIRs for a period of three years. Thus, we contribute by providing:

- A data-driven approach for enabling a recent macroscopic view of IoT botnet propagation strategies over the global IPv4 address space for the last three years.
- Profiling of AS structural properties with respect to inter-domain routing policies and further relating their tolerance with respect to hosting IoT botnet activity.
- A solid understanding of IoT botnet activity within individual ASes via quantifying their persistence and duration as well as attributing vital structural components such as malware downloaders.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section II provides background information on Inter-domain routing and an overview of related work. The datasets and methodology utilised in this work are described in Section III. Section IV is dedicated to presenting our findings. Finally, Section V summarises and concludes this work.

II. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

A. Autonomous Systems (ASes) & Inter-domain routing

An Autonomous System (AS) refers to a collection of Internet Protocol (IP) prefixes that are controlled by network operators and function under a unified and well-defined routing policies. The Regional Internet Registry (RIR) assigns an Autonomous System Number (ASN) to each AS, considering it as a distinctive identifier for the network. The ASN is a 32-bit integer that is globally unique and is used to distinguish an AS from other ASes on the Internet.

Packet forwarding across the Internet is underpinned by inter-domain routing between ASes achieved currently through the Border Gateway Protocol (BGP). Essentially, the BGP protocol was designed to govern the packet forwarding and route selection among ASes according to AS-level policies. Hence, BGP-enabled routers keep a table containing the AS path necessary to reach a specific IP prefix as advertised by a neighboring peer AS. One of the most distinguishing characteristics of BGP is its ability to allow individual ASes to engineer their own administrative policy for establishing the optimal route and handling the broadcasting and acceptance of route announcements.

In parallel, through the BGP instrumentation conducted by each AS, ASes establish business relationships, broadly categorized into two types: (i) customer-to-provider (c2p) and (ii) peer-to-peer (p2p). Under the c2p relationship, an AS must acquire transit services to reach parts of the internet

outside its ownership or that are inaccessible via its customers. Conversely, in a p2p scenario, two collaborating ASes mutually access each other's customer networks, typically in a reciprocal exchange. Moreover, the business relationships among the ASes often determine the flow of inter-AS traffic on the Internet. A common way for an IoT botmaster to expand their botnet network is by performing BGP prefix hijacking. This method involves acquiring control of IP address blocks without the approval of legal owners and exploiting a variety of BGP routines particularly on advertising bogus or illegitimate AS-level paths [6].

B. Related Work

Work in [2], [4], [7] aimed to identify the fundamental characteristics of botnets, showing a significant concentration in a few countries, and revealing ASes that embrace malicious activities. However, neither of these studies delved into the presence of botnets across individual ASes nor considered the specific prefixes announced by ASes, as we have done in our work. The work proposed in [8] concentrates on creating security rating systems for AS reputation in order to identify poorly managed or malicious networks. However, they do not provide any insights into the particular network characteristics that often harbor botnet activities. Similarly, the research presented in [9] developed various metrics for assessing reputation that focus solely on the density of abuse and consider some features of hosting providers. However, unlike the aforementioned studies, our study aims to investigate the structural characteristics of ASes and identify their explicit impact on IoT botnet activity.

Most studies focusing on AS-level measurements have examined security best practices within ASes using metrics derived from external sources of abuse data (e.g., [9], [10]), and have analysed AS structural properties from a business viewpoint, in which security practices were only tangentially addressed (e.g., [11], [12]). Nonetheless, to the best of our knowledge, the majority of recent and past researches have not successfully identified how the structural attributes of an AS impact its tolerance to IoT botnet activity. In addition, our work seeks to bridge this gap by analysing the interplay between the AS-level properties and IoT botnet activities. This unique approach helps to enhance our understanding of how the inherent characteristics of an AS can impact its susceptibility to IoT botnet attacks, hence paving the way for more effective mitigation strategies.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION & METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Description

Throughout our observations, we have gathered 1.4 million payloads produced by various IoT botnet families such as Mirai, Gafgyt and Bashlite, which aimed to recruit new IoT devices into their networks. As detailed in Table I, our data originated from 1.8 million unique IP addresses distributed over 8K ASes in 193 countries, covering a period of three years from January 2020 to January 2023. During our observation, we managed to observe 3.8 million malicious events

CTI data				BGP data			
Observation Period				CAIDA's ASRank			Shadowserver
01/01/2020 - 06/01/2023				Providers	Customers	Peers	Collected prefixes
IP addresses	Malicious events	ASes	Payloads	37,710	116,887	247,800	652,492
1.8M	3.8M	8K	1.4M				

TABLE I. Overview of CTI feeds and BGP data, CTI feeds captured by 40 globally distributed honeypots operated by Okta. BGP data acquired from CAIDA and Shadowserver, illustrates the overall number of AS links and prefixes within our dataset.

generated by IoT based botnet ranging between reconnaissance and infection activities.

BGP routing data: we leveraged CAIDA's ASRank¹ project to obtain inter-domain data. It involves retrieving the neighbors and respective ranks of each individual AS. We utilised such data to determine the degree of AS and identify the nature of their neighboring ASes. The degree metric of AS effectively estimates an AS's size and routing capacity, indicating its role in global Internet traffic routing [11]. Moreover, we used data from the Shadowserver Foundation in order to determine the IP prefixes announced by every distinct AS within our dataset. The ASN report from Shadowserver enumerates all the Classless Inter-Domain Routing (CIDR) blocks that an AS routes. The observed ASes advertised a total of 652,492 prefixes, as shown in Table I.

```
GET/cgi-bin/supervisor/CloudSetup.cgi?exefile=
cd /tmp;rm -rf *; wget http://X.X.X.X/bins
/ayylmao420kekuaintge -O 27.x; chmod 777
27.x; ./27.x avtech; echo keksec HTTP/1.1
```

Fig. 1: A sample of a malicious payload captured by distributed attack honeypots.

The captured payloads include shell commands and embedded URLs that are designed to lead the victim into downloading malicious binaries. Through using regular expression, we obtained the URLs from the payloads in order to identify botnet loaders. Code listing in Fig. 1 depicts an example of a malicious payload captured by the attack honeypot aiming an AVTech device. As illustrated, the sample malicious code includes a URL that directs the vulnerable IoT device to download binaries from a certain domain we have anonymized. Furthermore, the detected payload incorporates a chmod command, specifically "chmod 777", which is executed after the binary is downloaded using 'wget'. By applying our proposed algorithm in our previous work [5], we have successfully identified a total of 21K bot loaders involved in IoT botnet activities.

B. Methodology

a) **IP address mapping:** was performed through associating a group of IP addresses engaged in botnet activity,

denoted as B , with their respective source ASes, denoted as (ASx) . Therefore, the notation $occ(B \in ASx)$ indicates the overall count of IP addresses in B that are announced by (ASx) . This mapping process facilitated the attribution of botnet activity to specific ASes, enabling further analysis and understanding of the botnet's network structure and geographical distribution. Thus, the formula to map IP addresses to their corresponding AS set is:

$$occ(B \in ASx) = |\{b \in B : b \text{ is announced by } ASx\}| \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $|\cdot|$ denotes the cardinality (or size) of a set.
- b represents an individual IP address in the set B .

b) **Graph connectivity:** based on the methodology of our previous work in [5], we have developed a graph depicting the connectivity between ASes harboring botnet loaders and ASes embracing bots. Our aim is to measure the degree centrality and betweenness of ASes hosting loaders. Furthermore, in this paper we have related the obtained degree centrality with the structural properties of ASes.

c) **AS degree:** was determined from our measurements for BGP inter-domain and calculated through summing the number of neighbors linked to a specific ASx , encompassing providers, customers and peers. Therefore, we define the total number of links associated with ASx as follows:

$$AS(d) = \mathbb{R}(r) + \mathbb{R}(c) + \mathbb{R}(p) \quad (2)$$

in which $\mathbb{R}(p)$ represents the overall number of providers linked to the AS, $\mathbb{R}(c)$ indicates the total count of customers associated with the AS and $\mathbb{R}(r)$ signifies the overall count of peers linked to the specific AS.

d) **IP addresses space:** to demonstrate the spread of IoT botnet-related activity across an AS's prefixes, the announced prefixes (Pm) for B are extracted to define the count of prefixes associated with ASx that are engaged in malicious activity $(Pm \in ASx)$. We then calculate the aggregate number of announced prefixes for each individual ASx leveraging data from Shadowserver, leading to $(Pt \in ASx)$. Hence, the abuse rate for ASx is given as:

$$M(ASx) = \frac{\#(Pm \in ASx)}{\#(Pt \in ASx)} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, we apply the Jenks Natural Breaks (JNB) algorithm, a one-dimensional clustering approach [13]. Our aim is to arrange values generated by $M(ASx)$ into classes

¹CAIDA: <https://www.caida.org/projects/ark/>

Class	Abuse ratio	Provider	Peer	Customer	Total degree	Hosted malware downloaders	Total ASes
1	0-14	3.2	35.7	19.2	58.1	12.3%	3370
2	15-31	2.4	13	5.6	21	17.3%	3855
3	32-50	2	9.5	3.9	15.4	23.8%	4172
4	51-100	1.8	5.7	2.1	9.6	46.6%	3749

TABLE II. Clustering abuse ratio of ASes into classes by JNB algorithm, considering the average for AS degree, providers, peers and customer ASes for each individual class, along with the overall count of ASes in each respective class.

based on one-dimensional parameter: abuse rate. It is accomplished by maximising the variation across different classes and simultaneously while minimising the variance within each individual class. Given a set of abuse rates M for various ASes and a number of classes k , the sum of squared deviations from the array's mean (SDAM), is given as:

$$SDAM = \sum_{i=1}^n (M(ASx_i) - \bar{M})^2 \quad (4)$$

Where:

- $M(ASx_i)$ is the abuse rate for the i^{th} AS.
- \bar{M} is the mean of all abuse rates.

The sum of squared deviations for each class (SDCM) is:

$$SDCM = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^n (M(ASx_{j,class}) - \bar{M}_{class})^2 \quad (5)$$

Where:

- $M(ASx_{j,class})$ is the abuse rate of the j^{th} AS in the specific class.
- \bar{M}_{class} is the mean of the abuse rates in that class.

e) **AS temporal length:** provides the duration of time that a specific AS was involved in botnet activity. Hence, we identify the earliest and the latest timestamps associated with botnet activities within the AS. The duration of the event in days can be calculated as follows:

$$Duration = (t_{end} - t_{start})/24 \quad (6)$$

where t_{start} : timestamp representing the inception of a botnet activity event in a specific AS. t_{end} : timestamp indicating the end of botnet activity event in that AS. Furthermore, we have related the AS-level temporal length with the output of the coefficient variation (CV) developed in our previous work to measure the effectiveness of an IP blacklist [4].

IV. RESULTS

A. AS-level attributes

Via the JNB algorithm, we manage to cluster the abuse ratio into four different classes and subsequently measure inter-domain routing properties of each individual class as depicted in Table II. Evidently, a significant percentage of malware downloaders reside on ASes characterised by a low AS degree.

Fig. 2: Time span for ASes embracing botnet activities, indicating that ASes with an extended duration exhibit to have a lower CV score.

For instance, class 4 contains ASes with the highest abuse ratio from 51 to 100. Such ASes connect with an average of 1.8 providers, 5.7 peers, and 2.1 customers. This class hosts a significantly higher number of bot loaders, reaching 46.6%. By comparing this class with others, we can clearly see a substantial increase in malicious activity. In parallel, Class 1 has a relatively low percentage of 12.3%, and Class 4 reaches 45.6%. Thus, demonstrating a strong correlation between the abuse ratio and the tendency of an AS to host malicious entities based on its structural properties. Furthermore, it is evident that ASes with higher abuse ratios tend to have lower average degrees, fewer customers, peers and providers. It is hence indicated that malicious actors exploit ASes that are more isolated in terms of Internet connectivity and host their base botnet infrastructure.

Based on the assessment of the AS temporal length in relation to active IoT botnet activities, as illustrated in Fig. 2, it was observed that 50% of ASes had activity spans of less than 100 days. The detected ASes averaged a CV score of 0.60, indicating that a small percentage of IP addresses associated with botnet activities located in such networks were detected by IP blacklists. Meanwhile, the average score for ASNs active beyond 100 days stood at 0.40, suggesting a higher likelihood of detection for malicious IP addresses engaged in botnet activities by IP blacklists. Generally, we note that a significant portion of botnet activity is carried out to circumvent certain AS security, assuring the transfer of vital entities, such as malware loaders within a time frame of around three months.

Fig. 3: Mean CV values for different active day intervals of ASes, a lower score of CV implies that higher proportion of blacklisted IPs while a high score lower proportion of IPs captured by blacklisted.

Upon conducting further analysis of our dataset, we have identified malicious activity carried out by infected IPs via correlating these activities with their originating ASes and the associated advertised IP prefixes through BGP announcements. Our analysis revealed that 26% of the ASes under observation had in excess of 50% of their originating IP prefixes engaged in malicious activity. These findings indicate that such networks were implicated in a range of cyber attacks (e.g., cryptojacking, ransomware), prompted by IoT-based botnets. Additionally, the characteristics of these ASes indicate that botmasters tend to exploit and target those ASes that have a limited count of providers and relatively weak BGP routing policies. These observations suggest that a substantial number of ASes engage in malicious activities due to a lack of robust security measures and AS-level policies. As shown in Fig. 3, we segmented AS temporal length into 90-day intervals, and we computed the mean CV score for each 90-day interval. Our aim was to measure the proportion of blacklisted IPs in relation to AS temporal length properties. Evidently, there is a decreasing trend of the CV score over time, indicating that AS-level policies and behaviour can dictate the likelihood of malicious IPs observed by blacklisted IP addresses. Hence, our findings suggest that blacklists are more likely to not capture IPs associated with less active ASes.

B. Botnet malware loaders

Botnet loaders serve as a crucial component in the botnet’s propagation strategy, as they are utilised to direct potential victims to connect to specific DNS domains and download the botnet malware. The detected botnet malware loaders that constitute botnet connectivity are dispersed among 1,082 ASes and 193 countries. Analysing the degree centrality of ASes harbouring botnet loaders and ASes tolerating bots may disclose structural aspects of a certain botnet network. Our findings indicate that ASes with the greatest degree of centrality are accessible to bots dwelling in over 200 ASes. AS211252, for example, is involved in the dissemination of malicious binaries to bots dispersed over 209 ASes. This

Fig. 4: The normalized betweenness value for ASes that host botnet loaders indicates that approximately 75% of these ASes have a zero value. It is attributed to the fact that these ASes primarily handle the routing of intra-AS traffic to bots.

Fig. 5: Distribution of degree centrality of ASes hosting botnet loaders, where the degree represents the connectivity of AS with other ASes. Only 32% of these ASes have a centrality degree > 0 , signifying their role in disseminating malware beyond their inter-domains.

indicates that these botnet loaders pose a substantial influence on the dissemination of malware over the Internet.

Through conducting an analysis of the betweenness centrality for ASes, it was revealed that 75% of ASes had a betweenness score of zero, as seen in Fig. 4. Thus, hostile bots seek out nearby exposed IoT devices in order to command them to retrieve malicious binaries from a malware loader residing within the same AS. AS17622, for instance, exhibits a betweenness score of 0 as bots communicate with botnet loaders that are hosted inside its ownership domain. It is argued that malicious actors pursue out ASes that have lax routing policies in order to accomplish this goal. Evidently, such behaviour is adopted in order to conceal the visibility of the traffic generated by their botnets throughout the Internet.

The analysis results of the degree centrality for bots and botnet loaders reveal that a limited proportion of botnet loaders exert influence throughout the botnet network as illustrated in Fig. 5. The higher degree of centrality seen on the left side of the figure reveals that only a small fraction of ASes (27%) house loaders with significant connectivity, implying these are

Ases	Loader Server	Bots	ASes sources
AS36352	39	132	51
AS53667	29	80	27
AS14061	24	153	78
AS211252	19	1103	209
AS211619	18	50	30

TABLE III. Top ranked ASes embrace malware downloaders corresponding with number of bots interacts with loaders and their originated ASes.

the central nodes in the network responsible for spreading malicious binaries. In contrast, as we move to the right, the centrality degree diminishes, showing that the majority of ASes have loaders with limited connectivity.

Table III presents the ASes with a high betweenness centrality. The table reveals a concentration of bot loaders within a subset of ASes, indicating that certain networks serve as significant hubs for the dissemination of malware. The presence of a high number of bots interacting with these loaders suggests that these ASes are not only distribution points but also active participants in the expansion of botnets. For instance, AS211252, which hosts a comparatively limited number of bot loaders, it exhibits a concerning high rate of bot interaction. This suggests that it acts as an important hub in the botnet infrastructure. The high number of originating ASes (209) associated with it also indicates that this AS has a wide-reaching impact, affecting a large and diverse network of compromised devices. Such findings underscore the complexity of cyber threat landscapes across networks, and it highlights the necessity for cyber defense strategies that not only consider the quantity of malicious entities but also their distribution and inter-connectivity within and across ASes.

V. CONCLUSION

Evidently, current threat vectors in the global Internet are underpinned by the evolution of modern IoT botnets that are capable of exploiting known and zero-day IoT-oriented vulnerabilities to carry out various large-scale attacks. The propagation and evolution of such botnets is strongly related with the dynamics of the Internet’s routing plane as dictated through the policy-based inter-domain routing conducted by ASes. In this paper, we provide a novel, data-driven study using real Internet measurements data over a three year period to investigate the macroscopic impact of AS-level routing on the evolution and propagation of IoT botnets. We thus profile the structural properties of ASes and assess their tolerance to harbour IoT botnet activity. Our findings indicate that malicious actors selectively target ASes with low AS degree to host their botnet malware downloaders and exploit ASes that are more isolated in terms of Internet connectivity to use them as server infrastructure for their IoT botnets. Moreover, our findings suggest that commonly used IP blacklists are more likely to not capture IPs associated with ASes that were active less than three months. It is also noteworthy that 68% of ASes exhibit a centrality degree of zero, emphasizing their significant role in the propagation of malware across

their related inter-domains. In general, we argue that our findings may substantially contribute towards the design of next generation Internet-wide cyber defence mechanisms and also aid in the area of inter-domain network management for Internet RIRs.

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